

Compliance of the meat supply chain and the slaughter of animals with the Halal standard

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Abstract. The application of halal standards in the food industry ensures the production of food products in accordance with Islamic dietary principles. The issue of trust in the halal status is more sensitive when choosing meat and meat products. The issue of trust in the halal status of products is the most sensitive when choosing meat and meat products. Therefore, manufacturers should standardize their products in order to be recognized on the market. To prevent contamination of halal products with non-halal ingredients, it is necessary to harmonize each phase of the supply chain with the guidelines of the standard. The guidelines contain specific requirements for each stage of the livestock farming conditions, the description of the slaughtering and processing, packaging, storage and transport procedures. This paper shows how the preservation of halal integrity is achieved, with a special emphasis on the process of animal slaughter. This is achieved by determining the critical points at which halal status can be violated, and the establishment of critical control points that will be monitored regularly. When the requirements of the halal standard are met at each stage of production, the right to a certificate is exercised, and meat and meat products contain a clearly displayed halal sign on the packaging.

1. Introduction

The demand for halal products among the growing trends in the global food market, including food in catering establishments, is particularly noteworthy. The word halal is of Arabic origin, in translation it means allowed, permitted and basically implies everything that is allowed to be consumed in the Islamic culture of nutrition. The opposite of halal is haram, which means everything that is forbidden to consume. Between these two terms is *meshbuh*, which means a product as suspicious due to its possibility of containing both *halal* and *haram*. In this case, Muslims must avoid the use of meshbuh products and seek additional status checks. The biggest problems arise precisely in the situation of suspicious, unclear products, because as such they lose their advantage when making purchase decisions with consumers looking for halal. The most sensitive area for consumers when it comes to halal food is the production of meat and meat products. Special requirements for meat are determined by legal regulations that all participants of the production chain are obliged to comply with. In order for meat to have halal status, one of the conditions is that the slaughter of animals must be carried out in accordance with Islamic regulations. The aim of this paper is to show the specific items that must be complied with in the Halalan Toyyiban Supply Chain when it comes to meat. The paper is based on the analysis of critical points and critical control points in the process of slaughtering

animals. If a particular procedure is haram, it prevents further processing of the meat or sale under the halal label.

2. Halal standard in the food supply chain

A halal standard is a document that clearly defines what is permissible (halal) and what is prohibited (haram) according to Islamic law. This Standard prescribes criteria for the implementation, certification and monitoring of the application of requirements, with the aim of ensuring compliance with Islamic rules [1]. The laws of food are explained through the Qur'an (the book of religion) and the Sunnah (the life, deeds and teachings of the Prophet Muhammad). Food is considered one of the most important factors in the interaction between different ethnic, social, and religious groups [2].

Halal Food Supply Chain (HFSC) includes all stages of the food production process, all the way to transport, reception and storage of raw materials, processing, packaging, storage of finished products and distribution [3]. Halal food manufacturers are required to apply the concept of tayyiban, which includes quality, nutritional value, hygiene and ethical practices of distribution of food products to consumers. Therefore, the modern approach in the development of the halal supply chain is also designated as the Halalan Toyyiban Supply Chain. This concept means that food is both halal and healthy to consume [4]. Also, in industrial practices, Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) and Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) standards are emphasized as additional guidelines for halal-based products throughout the supply chain process [5]. Hygiene, sanitation and food safety are the basic prerequisites for the preparation of halal food. All food safety procedures must be suitable for use in the halal food sector [6].

2. Meat production within Halalan Toyyiban Supply Chain

In order for meat to have halal status, three basic conditions must be met: The meat must come from animals that are allowed for consumption, the animals must be fed with permitted food and the slaughter of animals must be carried out in accordance with Islamic regulations. Meat without halal status is divided into two categories: meat from animals that are prohibited for consumption and meat from permitted animals that have been given components of animal origin in their diet, or slaughter has not been carried out in accordance with Islamic rules [3]. According to the standard of General Requirements for Halal Food, the following animals are considered halal: cattle, sheep, goats, camels, chickens, geese, ducks and turkeys, non-predatory wild animals such as deer, antelope, wild cattle, non-predatory birds, such as pigeons, sparrows, quails, ostriches. All types of fish with or without scales, fish eggs, prawns, and all other aquatic animals and their products. Animals that are considered non-halal are: pigs, dogs and their offspring; animals that have not been slaughtered according to Islamic rules; dead animals; land animals with long sharp teeth or tusks used to kill prey or for self-defense such as bears, elephants, monkeys and related families, wolves, lions, tigers, panthers, cats, jackals, foxes, squirrels, marten, martens, badgers, crocodiles, alligators and others; predatory birds with sharp claws, such as hawks, falcons, eagles, vultures, crows, ravens, owls; pests and poisonous animals such as rats, centipedes, scorpions, snakes, wasps, mice and other similar animals; animals that are considered disgusting such as lizards, snails, insects and their larval stages, and other similar animals; animals (including birds and insects) that are forbidden to kill in Islam, such as woodpeckers, ants and bees; donkeys and mules; animals that have been eaten by predatory animals, animals that use their heads to hit each other, animals that fall (due to injury,

blow or disease), animals that have been killed by a blow; halal animals, but which are deliberately and continuously fed harmful substances that are not suitable for their nature or are considered unclean. All toxic aquatic animals that are harmful to health are considered non-halal, unless the toxic and harmful substances have been removed [6].

In order to obtain Halal certification, the entire supply chain, from farm to fork, must be halal. The most important factors affecting the halal meat supply chain are the risks of cross-contamination during the entire process, starting from raw materials to finished products. Cross-contamination is defined as the physical transfer of harmful bacteria from one person, object or place to another. In the context of the halal principle, cross-contamination occurs when halal products come into direct contact with non-halal foods or ingredients at any stage of the supply chain [5]. In the production of high-quality meat according to the Standard, the process starts from the origin of the animals, whereby good breeding practices, pre-slaughter procedures, slaughter process, and post-slaughter procedures must be taken into account [7].

2.1 Animal husbandry under Halalan Toyyiban Supply Chain

Livestock farmers should ensure all farm conditions, including distance from pig farms in the case of mixed livestock farming, general animal welfare and vaccination regulations [8]. Each animal should be assigned a unique identification number, and all relevant data on health status and veterinary interventions should be recorded [9]. Vehicles and containers used for the transport of animals should be designed, constructed and equipped according to the specifics of the species being transported (size and weight). Special care must be taken to avoid injury to animals by using safe and smooth parts that do not have sharp protrusions. Vehicle structures should protect against adverse weather conditions and reduce the possibility of animals escaping. They should also be designed to allow thorough cleaning and disinfection, include an adequate ventilation system, food and water equipment if necessary [10]. Indoor, air quality, temperature and humidity should be maintained at a level that does not adversely affect animal health. Animal welfare is often linked to meat quality. Poorly treated and abused animals suffer from fatigue, bruising or injury, which can lead to poor quality raw meat. Injured animals tend to have higher levels of stress and develop an increased amount of glycogen in their blood over time, which causes the meat to be dark, hard, and dry. Halal animal nutrition is based on plant ingredients without additives of animal origin, which reduces the risk of Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy. If there is a suspicion that the animal has been fed such food or has ingested other impurities, it must be fed the correct food for as many days as necessary to purify its body [3]. Recommended poultry feed should be free of animal by-products or other waste materials.

2.1 Slaughter of large and small livestock

Slaughter sites should be exclusively for halal slaughter and must meet the requirements of the Prerequisite Programs (PrPs), defined by Codex alimentarius – CAC/RCP 1, ISO 22 000 or ISO/TS 22 002 (all parts). The physical conditions in slaughtering places must meet national legal requirements. The general requirements for halal slaughter include that the animal must be halal (allowed), healthy, confirmed by a veterinary examination and must be alive at the time of slaughter [3]. *Zabiha* or *Dhabiha* is a term that in Islamic legislation refers to meat that has been slaughtered in the halal manner. The word *Dhabh* means the process by which an animal is prepared for consumption [11].

The person performing the slaughter must be an adult Muslim who is mentally healthy and fully understands the basic rules and conditions related to halal slaughter. The person carrying out the slaughter must be professional and experienced in relation to the slaughter process, as

well as meet the requirements related to health, general hygiene and food safety rules. The slaughter procedure is carried out in such a way that the animal is restrained and placed on its left side, facing the Qibla (in the direction of Mecca). Care should be taken to reduce the suffering of the animal while it is being placed, and not to keep it in this position for too long. The slaughterman begins the process by saying the tesmiyya, i.e. the ritual words “*Bismillahi Allahu ekber*” (“*In the name of God, God is the greatest!*”).

Figure 1 shows the process of halal slaughter. The act of slaughter begins with an incision in the neck just below the glottis (Adam's apple), that is, after the glottis in animals with a long neck. In order for the slaughter to be completely successful, the trachea (Arabic *halqum*), the esophagus (Arabic *mari*) and both carotid arteries and jugular veins (Arabic *wadajain*) are cut (Figure 1)[6, 12]. Carotid arteries and jugular veins deliver oxygenated blood to the brain, and

Figure 1. Method of slaughtering cattle (MS 1500:2009)

by cutting them, the animal dies due to lack of circulating blood and consequent cerebral anoxia [13]. The instrument (knife) used for slaughter must be sharp, made of stainless steel. Cutting must be done with a blade and not with weight or pressure, nor can bones, nails or teeth be used as tools for slaughter. The incision must be on the front above the chest, not on the side of the neck or back. Before any part of the carcass is cut, peeling of the skin, scalding or removal of feathers in poultry, complete death of the animal must be ensured [6, 12]. The whole process should not take more than 40 seconds, and the animal should not be injured due to improper position or high pressure [3]. According to the UAE.S. 993:2022 standard, the amount of blood during bleeding must be monitored and if a smaller amount of blood than normal is observed due to cardiac arrest, the carcass is treated as non-halal.

Stunning implies the procedure of disabling animals before slaughter (Malaysian Halal Protocol, 2011). All methods of stunning and loss of consciousness are prohibited. However, when the use of an electric shock becomes necessary to calm or prevent violent behavior of the animal, it should be aligned with the permissible period and values of the electric current. When stunning is permitted, the following conditions must be met: the animals must remain alive after stunning and before they are slaughtered. If death is determined before slaughter, they are considered fatally struck animals. It is forbidden to incapacitate an animal with a slaughter tool, cutter, hammer or in other ways [6]. If a stunning procedure is performed, slaughter must be performed immediately after loss of consciousness, and the animal must not regain consciousness before death caused by slaughter occurs. It is recommended that halal

Figure 2. Standing box for restraining livestock

slaughterhouses be equipped with specialized restraint devices that allow the animal to be safely kept in the correct slaughter position without the need for stunning.

Such devices, known as "halal slaughter boxes", are designed to immobilize the animal to prevent its injury and allow for the proper act of slaughter. The head and neck of the animal remain outside the box, fixed with holders, to enable precise cutting of the cervical vessels in accordance with halal standards (Figure 2). At least two surveillance cameras must be installed on the production lines near the area where the animals lose consciousness (each with an independent system). It is necessary to record the process to determine whether standard stunning procedures cause the death of the animal. Also, there must be adequate storage capacity for film recordings (at least 90 days) that are available on demand (UAE.S 993:2022, general guidelines and Appendix A).

2.2. Slaughter of poultry

In industrial slaughterhouses, poultry slaughter lines are usually automated, and there are also automatic stunning systems. In manual slaughter, the person slaughtering must properly tighten the head of the poultry and cut the neck with a sharp knife (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Method of slaughtering poultry (MS 1500:2009)

In the case of automated slaughter, the operator of the mechanical knife must be a Muslim and say "Bismillahi Allahu akbar" when starting the knife. This procedure must be repeated for each individual act of slaughter, and the use of automatic devices for pronouncing this expression is not permitted. The knife used must be sharp, made of stainless steel and suitable for cleaning. If the mechanical knife fails to properly slaughter an individual, manual slaughter must be carried out. The bleeding period must last at least 180 seconds [3].

2.3. Slaughter of other animals

No slaughter is required for fish. They need to be taken out of the water while they are still alive so that death occurs outside the water. A fish is not halal if it is found dead and floating at the time of fishing. Poisonous and sick fish are not halal. Other animals, which are hunted by a Muslim person, are considered halal if a tesmiyya is pronounced before killing and the animal is hit by the sharp edge of the weapon [6].

3. Haram Analysis Critical Control Points

In order to establish a system of control and monitoring of production processes and confirm the halal status of products, it is necessary to implement the HrACCP system (Haram Analysis Critical Control Points). HrACCP includes the analysis of the entire production chain through all stages, from primary agricultural production, through processing and packaging, to the distribution of products to the end user. The aim of this analysis is to identify potential points at each stage that could lead to non-compliance with halal standards. Therefore, it is advisable to perform haram analysis to identify haram critical control points. This term is modeled on HACCP (Hazard Analysis Critical Control Points), a system that deals with the identification, assessment and control of food safety hazards. The methodology and approach of both systems are identical, with the difference that HACCP identifies food safety hazards, while HrACCP analyzes critical points that could lead to haram [3, 14]. The principle of determining haram critical control points (HrCCPs) using a tree, based on the standard **MS 1500:2009 Halal food - Production, preparation, handling and storage**, shown in Figure 4.

Figure 1. Halal Critical Control Point Decision Tree for Slaughtering animal (Ramalingam et al, 2012)

This standard requires compliance with MS 1480 – HACCP or MS 1514 – Good Manufacturing Practice. On Figure 4 is shown the HACCP concept is adapted to halal standards to identify and eliminate possible impurities or haram, with zero tolerance for non-compliance with Islamic food laws. The process involves monitoring critical control points for haram and taking corrective action in case of deviation [15].

3.1. Halal control points in meat industry

Halal control points (HCPs) can be determined for each stage of the process. HCP for the meat processing is shown on Figure 5 [2].

Figure 2. Halal control points in meat processing (Riaz and Chaudry, 2004)

HCP1 means that the animal must belong to species that are halal (allowed) for consumption in Islam. HCP2 refers to the treatment of animals. Animals must be treated so that they are not stressed or excited before slaughter. HCP3 refers to stunning. It is recommended that animals be slaughtered without stunning, but some non-lethal stunning methods can be used. HCP4 refers to the sharpness of the knife. The knife must be sharp so that the animal does not feel pain when cutting. HCP5 refers to the person who performs the slaughter and requires that the person performing the slaughter must be of legal age, mentally capable and familiar with the slaughter process. HCP6 – The act of slaughter. Rapid cutting of the neck, trachea, esophagus, carotids, jugular veins, without reaching the bone in the neck. HCP7 refers to the obligatory pronunciation of God's name while cutting the neck. HCP8 refers to the post-slaughter procedure. It is not allowed to cut off parts such as ears, horns or legs before the animal is completely dead. When the bleeding stops, the heart stops and the animal dies, further processing of the carcass can be started. HCP9 - packaging and labelling. The meat is packed in clean packages and boxes. Appropriate markings with a halal sign are placed on the packages [2].

4. Certification procedure and halal sign

In order to obtain a halal certificate, it is necessary to implement the mentioned HrACCP system. HrACCP is based on several principles: haram analysis (a flow chart is used for the identification and analysis of prohibited substances), determination of critical control points where halal status can be lost, i.e. haram occurs, and establishment of monitoring procedures, establishment of procedures for verification and establishment of a documentation system. The process of certification of halal products is carried out by organizations authorized by the Islamic religious community.

The Halal Quality Certification Agency conducts the certification process based on a uniform procedure [16]. The applicant (interested organization) submits a request to the Agency and submits the necessary documentation. The Agency reviews the submitted documents, and if all requirements are met, sends the applicant an offer for halal certification. After the applicant accepts the offer, the Agency and the applicant conclude a contract for a period of three years. The halal certificate is issued for a period of one year, and in the remaining

two years of the contract, the Agency conducts announced or unannounced supervisory audits and laboratory analyzes to confirm that the organization still meets all the requirements of the Standard (Halal Quality Certification Agency, 2024b). Laboratory analyzes are divided into mandatory and recommended. Mandatory analyzes include checking the presence of the following ingredients: pork DNA, protein and pork fats/lipids, alcohol (ethanol), genetically modified (GM) raw materials and pork proteins and fats in animal feed and poultry feed. Recommended analyses include microbiological, chemical and physical analyses. Recommended analyses become mandatory if, during an audit or other procedures, it is determined that the product does not meet health regulations. Recertification is carried out at the end of the certification cycle, which lasts three years, with the signing of a new contract. The certification audit is performed in organizations whose certificate has not been suspended or withdrawn. An organization that does not renew the certificate loses the right to use it and display the halal sign [3].

The Agency has developed a trademark that represents the Agency's logo and is used to designate halal products (Figure 6). The halal label is registered with the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), which prohibits its use without the Agency's permission. The halal label can be used by manufacturers who have successfully applied the Standard and by sellers and distributors who have received written approval from the Agency. The use of the Halal sign without the prior written approval of the Agency is strictly prohibited and legally punishable (Halal Quality Certification Agency, 2024c).

Figure 3. Halal mark of the Agency for Halal Quality Certification (Certification Agency Halal quality, 2024)

5. Conclusion

Among consumers who consume halal, the most prevalent demand is for halal meat and meat products. There is a lack of knowledge about what the Halal standard entails. On the other hand, there is a lack of trust in halal status on the part of consumers. For this reason, it is very important to understand the importance of implementing the HrACCP system (Haram Analysis Critical Control Points) and establishing critical control points in the flow diagram of the entire process where haram substances may appear or the status of halal may be lost through a certain improper procedure. First of all, it is important that the meat comes from a halal animal, which is farming in humane and acceptable conditions. The animal should be killed in a halal way, which often involves manual slaughter with a sharp knife according to a well-known procedure for a particular animal, all in order to reduce the suffering of the animal. When slaughtering, it is necessary that the person performing this procedure be a Muslim and that he pronounces the *Tasmiyyah*. It is important to respect the period of bleeding and not to start processing the

carcass until the animal is completely dead. In addition to this, meat and meat products should meet food safety requirements: microbiological, chemical and physical characteristics must not endanger the health and life of consumers. Finally, the use of the halal label on meat and meat products is allowed to producers only if they have implemented the Halal standard in their company or to distributors who have received the written approval of the Agency. The use of the halal sign without meeting these conditions is illegal and punishable by law.

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